

Project No.:	644606
Project acronym:	Photonics4All
Project title:	EU-wide outreach for promoting photonics to young people, entrepreneurs and the general public
Instrument:	Coordination and Support Action
Programme:	ICT-26-2014: Photonics KET
Start date of project:	01.01.2015
Duration:	24 Months

Deliverable 4.6

Summary of gained collaborations with local authorities/policy makers and sponsoring companies

Deliverable Name	Summary of gained collaborations with local authorities/policy makers and sponsoring companies
Deliverable Number	4.6
Work Package	4
Associated Task	4.3 – “cooperation with other relevant authorities and organisations”
Covered Period	01.01.2015-31.12.2016
Due Date	M23 (November 2016)
Submission Date	02.12.2016
Deliverable Lead Partner	SEZ
Deliverable Author	Dorothea Haas, Aude Péliisson-Schecker (SEZ), Maria Bondani (CNR), Aurèle Adam (TUD), Johannes Verst (OND), Pearl John (UoS), Dusan Chorvat (ILC), Fiona Gerente (OV), Ulrich Trog (PhAu), Petra Bindig (EaPS)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	x
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Table of Content

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Collaboration with EYEST _{vzw}	3
3 Cooperation with public authorities and policy makers	11
3.1 Austria	11
3.2 France	12
3.3 Germany.....	13
3.4 Italy.....	14
3.5 Slovakia.....	14
3.6 Sweden	16
3.7 The Netherlands.....	17
3.8 United Kingdom.....	18
3.9 Multilateral cooperation	19
4 Cooperation with photonics enterprises/industry	19
4.1 Germany.....	20
4.2 France	22
4.3 Slovakia.....	24
4.4 Great Britain	26
4.5 Sweden	27
4.6 The Netherlands.....	27
4.7 Multilateral cooperation	27
5 Summary	28

List of Figures

Figure 1: The “Photonics Explorer” kit.	3
Figure 2: Impressions from a children’s university in Kista (Sweden).....	9
Figure 3: Group picture of participating students in the photonics workshop provided by Eyestvzw team at the ICT2015 exhibition.	10
Figure 4: Photonics4All leaflet in Photonics explorer kit.	10
Figure 5: Young Visitor at the Long Night of Research 2016.....	11
Figure 6: Cooperation with authorities in Slovakia.....	15
Figure 7: Light festival in the DOME OF VISIONS in 2015.....	17
Figure 8: Logos of partners and sponsors of the European Start-up challenge.....	20
Figure 9: The winner of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge Sicoya GmbH	20
Figure 10: Impressions from the 3rd innovation workshop – “Precision mounting of photonic micro systems”	21
Figure 11: The pitch award winner of INPHO 2016 is Chronocam	24
Figure 12: Light show at the main hall of Science centre Aurelium	25
Figure 13: Presentation of Photoneo s.r.o. during the Day of Photonics 2016	26
Figure 14 Elks-Smith Landscaping Designers visit the ORC, and Booth at RHS Tatton Park Garden Show	26
Figure 15 Media Coverage of the Reflecting Photonics Garden at Tatton Park	27

List of Tables

Table 1: Summary of events where the photonics explorer kit was disseminated and used.....	8
Table 2: List of participants to Opticsvalley’s Photonics Venture Summit – pitching start-ups.....	23
Table 3: List of Start-ups pitching at INPHO Venture Summit in Bordeaux	24

1. Introduction

In order to increase the impact of Photonics4All activities and tools it was foreseen to establish and use collaborations with:

- 1) Non-profit organization **EYEST**_{vzw} (Photonics Explorer Kit),
- 2) Local authorities and **policy** makers,
- 3) Photonics **enterprises**/industry.

The following chapters summarize the achievements of this task and demonstrate which collaborations could be established along the project and how these were particularly gained.

All Photonics4All partners were involved in that task, namely Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum (SEZ), OpTecNet Deutschland (OND), Opticsvalley (OV), PhotonicsSweden (EaPS), Photonics Austria (PhAu), the Delft University of Technology (TUD), the University of Southampton (UoS), the International Laser Center (ILC) and the Institute of Photonics and Nanotechnology of the National Research Council (CNR).

2. Collaboration with EYEST_{vzw}

The development of an intra-curricular educational kit named “Photonics Explorer” was the result of a pan-European public private partnership funded by the EC in an FP7 project 'EXPEKT'. The Belgium based non-profit organization, EYEST_{vzw} (Excite Youth for Engineering Science and Technology), was established to sustain and distribute the kit beyond the EU project. The organization currently offers the developed kit free-of-charge to schools, thereby increasing the awareness of students about photonics and promoting an interest in science in general.

Figure 1: The “Photonics Explorer” kit.

During the proposal preparation Photonics4All has received a letter of interest from EYEST_{vzw}. This has been the stepping stone towards a fruitful collaboration. In the second consortium meeting of Photonics4All, Ulrich Trog from Photonics Austria was so kind to provide an internal training for all members of the Photonics4All project. He is well experienced in providing training about the tool as he usually coordinates the Photonics Explorer teacher training courses in Austria. The following table presents the activities where the Photonics Explorer tool was disseminated and used to inspire young people, teachers and the general public with photonics. 62 events are listed in that table

Description	Type of Activity	Date, Location
Photonics Teacher Training for physics lessons – the tool was used to train teachers to use it during their physics lessons.	Teacher Training	04.+05.02.2016, Wolfsberg, Austria
Photonics Teacher Training for physics lessons – the tool was used to train teachers to use it during their physics lessons.	Teacher Training	24.02.2015, Salzburg, Austria
Photonics Teacher Training for physics lessons – the tool was used to train teachers to use it during their physics lessons.	Teacher Training	09.06.2015, Vienna, Austria
Presentation of Photonics4All project and Photonics Explorer tool kit at “Science on Stage” at Queen Mary University London. A list was sent to EYEst on the teachers wanting further information.	Teacher Training	17-20.06.2015, London, UK
Photonics Teacher Training for physics lessons – the tool was used to train teachers to use it during their physics lessons.	Teacher Training	19.06.2015, Voigtsberg, Austria
KIT Open Day, walk of innovations	Dissemination	27.06.2015, Karlsruhe, Germany
Royal Horticulture Society Tatton Park Garden Show – “Reflecting Photonics” Show Garden. The Photonics Explorer kit was demonstrated.	Campaign	22.07-24.07.2015, Cheshire, United Kingdom
Two workshops ‘Light and Colours’ using lenses and diffraction gratings from the kit	Children University	27.+29.07.2015, Graz, Austria

5 workshops at the KIT-children's university for 7-13 age pupils, lenses, fibre LED-modules and colour filters were used as experiments	Children's University	04.08.-20.08.2015, Karlsruhe, Germany
Organization of a hands-on exhibition and IYL 2015 show – almost all modules were used to demonstrate photonics	Campaign	05.09.2015, Stockholm, Sweden
Teacher training workshops for Photonics Explorer. 160 participants considering low- and upper-secondary school teachers, with 12 training days in 4 different locations.	Teacher training	08.09.-16.12.2015 Bergamo, Como, Milano and Trento
LE FRONTIERE DELLA LUCE: Viaggio alla scoperta della luce estrema	Campaign	08.10.2015, Rome, Italy
Presentation of the Kit on a booth in a hospital during the "Fête de la Science" week	Campaign	10.10.2015, Evry, France
Two one-day teacher training sessions in parallel to the students' congress in Bratislava	Teacher training	14+15.10.2015, Bratislava, Slovakia
ICT 2015 Innovate, Connect, Transform	Dissemination	20.-22.10.2015, Lisbon, Portugal
Presentation of Photonics Explorer kit to the Director of the Mathematics and Science Learning Centre (Teacher Training Centre, Southampton).	Dissemination	06.11.2015, Southampton, United Kingdom
Meeting of the Institute of Physics, Stimulating Physics Network, Teaching and Learning Coaches.	Teacher Training	10.11.2015, Southampton, United Kingdom
Photonics Teacher Training for physics lessons – the tool was used to train teachers to use it during their physics lessons.	Teacher Training	20.11.2015, Linz, Oberösterreich, Austria
Light week in the Dome of Visions, including experiments for the general public and children	Campaign	23.-28.11.2015, Stockholm, Sweden
Photonics Explorer promoted and demonstrated to South East Physics	Dissemination	11.12.2015, UK

Network Outreach Director and Officers. Request for 3 kits to work with.		
Photonics Teacher Training for physics lessons – Session for the Institute of Physics Capital Physics Project, Teaching and Learning Coaches	Teacher Training	18.01.2016, United Kingdom
Photonics Outreach Activity with Oasis Academy Mayfield and Redbridge Community Schools using elements of the Photonics Explorer kit	Dissemination	22.01.2016, Southampton, UK
Southampton Science and Engineering Festival, Family Day. Hands-on Optics Booth for general public.	Dissemination	12.03.2016, Southampton, United Kingdom
Hands-on Optics Workshops, Thomas Hardy School.	Children's University	19.04.2016, Southampton, UK
Hands-on Photonics Workshop - Children's University Ash Manor School - STEM Festival.	Dissemination	25.04.2016, Southampton, UK
Photonics Outreach Stand at Doctoral College Engagement Showcase, including hand-on activities to promote photonics outreach to University staff and students.	Dissemination	17.05.2016, Southampton, UK
Children's university	Children's University	01.06.2016, Kista, Sweden
Teachers Event - OCR Exam Board Conference - Light Show and Promoting Photonics Explorer Kit, disseminating App, Bookmarks and Study Photonics.	Dissemination	16.06.2016, London, United Kingdom
Joint International Physics Summer School	High-school students	20-24.06.2016, Como, Italy
Institute of Physics Stimulating Physics Network Teacher training Day. Photonics Workshop.	Dissemination	24.06.2016, United Kingdom
Six distinct optics and photonics hands-on interactive activities for 120 pupils 13-14 years old	Children's University	11.07.2016, Southampton, United Kingdom

Photonics Explorer Booth at a Teacher's Residential Course, University of Southampton	Dissemination	02.08.2016 Southampton, UK
2 workshops at the KIT-children's university for 7-13 age pupils, lenses, fibre LED-modules and colour filters were used as experiments	Children's University	09+11.08.2016, Karlsruhe, Germany
"Officina Scuola", Teacher training workshop for Photonics Explorer. 50 participants considering low- and upper-secondary school teachers and Photonics demonstrations for general public	Teacher training	09.09.2016, Italy
Workshops 'Light and Colours' using lenses and diffraction gratings from the kit	Children's University	26.-27. September 2016, Graz, Austria
In connection with the researcher's night, 2 groups of children aged 14-16 years and the other 16-17 years could experiment with light	Children's University	30.09.2019, Stockholm, Sweden
European Researchers' Night – stand dedicated to Photonics Explorer kit	Dissemination	30.09.2016, Slovakia
Teacher training workshops for Photonics Explorer. 110 participants considering low- and upper-secondary school teachers: 7 trainings in five different locations.	Teacher training	17.10.-23.11.2016 Bergamo, Como, Milano, Torino and Trento
Presentation of the project Photonics4All & the explorer kit at the opening day of the DOC opening "Dutch Optics Center", TUD being partner of it.	Dissemination	19.10.2016, Delft, The Netherlands
One-day training for secondary-school teachers	Teacher Training	9.11.2016, Trnava, Slovakia
Photonics Explorer workshop in collaboration with the Institute of Physics Stimulating Physics Network. Kits distributed to teachers.	Teacher Training	17.11.2016, UK
Conference of Physics teachers in the Netherlands: presentation of our App, photonics explorer kit, videos and everything	Teacher Training	16-17.12.2016, Delft, The Netherlands

they would need in class to talk about photonics		
Distribution of Photonics Explorer kits among 14 primary and secondary schools (for approx. 1 month/school)	Dissemination	2015-2016, Slovakia
Eyest offers from May 2016 on the Photonics4All app on its website and includes leaflet for app download in its photonics explorer kit	Teacher trainings	2016 and following

Table 1: Summary of events where the photonics explorer kit was disseminated and used.

Thanks to the **Photonics4All activities**, more than **290 photonics** explorer kits of Eyest_{vzw} were sold and distributed. This number represents about **10% of the total number of kits distributed so far** (Status on 02.12.2016: 2724 kits).

- Austria: Photonics Austria has conducted teacher training programs using about **60 photonics explorer kits** and trained dozens of teachers
- France: the Kit was presented during a campaign activity during the French “Fête de la Science” week in October 2015. Opticsvalley bought **one kit** for this occasion.
- Germany: In Germany the children’s universities took place at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, former University of Karlsruhe (KIT) in 2015 and 2016. SEZ bought **2 photonics explorer kits** for this activity.
- Italy: CNR became *Local Associated Partner with EYEST_{vzw}* and now, it is one of the responsible organisations for teacher training sessions and distribution of the Photonics Explorer kits in Italy. In total, circa 150 kits were distributed.
- In Slovakia, three one-day teacher training sessions were conducted for 34 teachers and Photonics **toolkits were distributed to 14 different schools** to enhance the education in physics (approx. 1 month at each school). Based on the requests from the teachers – attendees of the Teacher training workshop, ILC decided (and recently agreed with EYEST) to fund the purchase of 10 Photonics Explorer kits that will be permanently distributed in selected Slovak schools in December 2016.
- Sweden: EaPS used diverse elements of the photonics explorer kit during this event and conducted experiments to demonstrate photonics concepts.
- The Netherlands: The Delft University of Technology has become the Local Associated Partner for the Netherlands and is responsible for teacher training and distribution of the Photonics Explorer kits in the Netherlands. So far **30 kits** have been acquired directly, **10** bought via a Dutch company (Focal, NL). The kit has been presented at several meetings involving companies (DOC opening at TNO, PhotonicsEvents in Veldhoven). Presentation to the Union of the Physics

Teachers is planned in December (2016) with a talk, a booth and hands-on demonstrations.

- United Kingdom: UoS promoted the Photonics Explorer kit to teachers on many occasions, e.g. on booths at “Science on Stage”, the RHS Tatton Park Garden Show and at residential courses for teachers arranged by the UoS and the IOP, passing on teacher’s contact details to Eyestvzw; 22 kits have been distributed; 6 kits were given to IOP Capital Teaching and Learning Coaches, (all experienced Physics teachers) and 11 kits were distributed to newly qualified school teachers who are part of the IOP’s Stimulating Physics Network. In addition, UoS purchased 2 **kits** for Schools that partnered with them during the Year of Light outreach activities and assisted with teacher training workshops, 1 kit for a Physics Outreach officer at the University of Leeds, and two further kits for the UoS’ Photonics Outreach Postgraduate student team. Purchase of kits was funded by the ‘National Future Photonics Manufacturing Hub’. Last but not least, UoS is now a Local Associated Partner with EYESTvzw responsible for teacher training and distribution of the Photonics Explorer kits in the UK.

Figure 2: Impressions from a children’s university in Kista (Sweden)

Multilateral cooperation: In the listing above, several activities & events are listed where the photonics explorer kit was used and presented by Photonics4All partners. Two activities deserve closer attention. First of all, together with the project GoPhoton! and Light2015, SEZ and UoS participated at the ICT2015 conference to make photonics more popular. The EYEST team brought the Photonics Explorer and the Photonics Innovator tool kits to the exhibition. Both kits were used to demonstrate experiments to the participants of the conference. In addition, a students’ workshop was organized in the frame of the exhibition (see picture below).

Figure 3: Group picture of participating students in the photonics workshop provided by Eyestvzw team at the ICT2015 exhibition.

Besides, Opticsvalley has contacted EYEST regarding the dissemination of the Photonics4All APP. Nathalie Debaes from EYEST has been very receptive and has suggested to help disseminate the APP through the distribution of the Photonics Explorer. The following leaflet is now included in the kit, with a QR code signposting to the APP.

Photonics4All app

"Photonics is the Science and technology of generating, controlling, and detecting Light."

Download our amazing App to learn more about Photonics!

The App consists of 5 modules. These modules include games and quizzes which makes our App fun and interesting. Test our App yourself! You can download it on GooglePlay Store.

Figure 4: Photonics4All leaflet in Photonics explorer kit.

3 Cooperation with public authorities and policy makers

3.1 Austria

The Long Night of Research is a national event to promote research to the general public. In the framework of this year's Long Night of Research on 22 April 2016, Photonics Austria in cooperation with JOANNEUM RESEARCH and the University of Applied Sciences Vorarlberg conducted activities to promote Photonics.

Figure 5: Young Visitor at the Long Night of Research 2016

In the framework of teachers trainings Photonics Austria cooperated with the regional teacher training organisations:

- Pädagogische Hochschule Steiermark
- Pädagogische Hochschule Salzburg
- Pädagogische Hochschule Oberösterreich
- Universität Wien, Österreichisches Kompetenzzentrum für Didaktik der Physik
- NAWI-Netzwerk Lavanttal
- ENERGIEFORUM Lipizzanerheimat

40 Photonics Explorer kits were sponsored by the regional government of Styria.

The Photonics boot camp was jointly organized and conducted with the Vienna University of Economics and Business.

The children's universities were jointly organized and conducted with the University of Graz and the University of Applied Sciences Vorarlberg.

The federal ministry of Transport, Innovation and Technology as well as the Federal Ministry of Education were instrumental in setting up the contacts with schools and teacher training organisations.

3.2 France

Photonics4All and Photonics in general have been promoted during the French national event “Fête de la Science” in October 2015. Opticsvalley held a booth on this occasion in the Evry (Paris region) public hospital. The objective was, on a Saturday, to promote Photonics to all the hospital patients and visitors.

In general, the project has been promoted to our local financiers which are the “Conseil Départemental de l’Essonne” and the “Conseil Régional d’Île de France”. This promotion has been done while sending them our annual reports and actions plans, and also giving them access to the dissemination tools.

Opticsvalley is in constant contact with the Paris regional authority (“Conseil Régional d’Île de France”) to promote Photonics and make sure it is well included in the regional policies. As a result, Optics and Photonics have been included by the Region as a horizontal theme in the RIS3 (Smart Specialization Strategies) priorities.

More information: <http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/regions/fr10?s3pv=4>

In July 2016, Opticsvalley has been labelled as an official thematic network in the French Tech initiative after having answered the January call for proposals to renew the network. This French Program gathers stakeholders of the start-ups French ecosystem (entrepreneurs, investors, designers, associations, public authorities, research institutions...) willing to promote the development and the innovation of French start-ups.

Photonics is now identified as a key enabling technology (KET), and is included in the “#IoT #Manufacturing” national network.

Concretely, this means that the French photonics start-ups and scale-ups will have more exposure to international market.

More information: <http://www.lafrenchtech.com/>

In the framework of our regular cooperation with local universities (e.g. Paris Sud, Université Paris Diderot), we also often presented the project and the tools.

Here are a few examples of policy makers / public authorities which have been invited and attended our events promoting Photonics:

- “Convention des adhérents Opticsvalley” – December 2015: David Ross, Mayor of Orsay (town near Opticsvalley) and Vice President in charge of Research & Innovation in the CAPS Urban Community

- Opticsvalley's "Photonisc Venture Summit" – June 2015: Jérôme Chartier, 1st Vice-President of the Conseil Régional d'Ile de France and François Durovray, President of the Conseil Départemental de l'Essonne
- French closing ceremony IYL – February 2016: Marie-Christine Lemardeley, 1st Deputy of Paris City Hall, in charge of high education, research and student life

Photonics4Investment in Bordeaux – October 2016: Nitán Pathak, Institutional Business Development at European Investment Fund ; Willy Van Puymbroek, Head of Unit in DG Connect European Commission ; Florence Forzy-Raffard, Councillor for International Economic Affairs and European Affairs at City of Bordeaux ; Anne-Laure Bedu, Councillor for Technology transfer, Innovation and Acceleration at Region Nouvelle-Aquitaine

3.3 Germany

SEZ has closely cooperated with the city of Karlsruhe to promote Photonics4All. For the children's universities in 2015 and 2016, SEZ was in an intense exchange with the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology to develop and conceptualize the best practices for the photonics workshops for children.

The two planned Photonics **Science-Slams** based on the very close co-operation between OND and the "Baden-Württemberg Stiftung gGmbH", one of Germany's biggest foundations for top-level research, education and society and culture. The foundation provides the slams with premises, their network in science and education etc.

Several universities and linked research institutes actively promoted the science slams, especially:

- Center of Optical Technologies, Aalen
- Humbold-Universität zu Berlin
- Institute for Laser Technology in Medicine and Measurement Technique, Ulm
- Institute of Applied Optics, Stuttgart
- Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
- Ludwig-Maximilian Universität München
- University of Applied Science, Aalen
- University of Heidelberg
- University of Konstanz
- University of Stuttgart

The first **Innovation Workshop** was organized in co-operation with Mikrosystemtechnik Baden-Württemberg e.V. (today: microTEC Südwest e.V.), a technology cluster in the field of microsystem technology as well as benefit from their expertise and some input of Baden-Württemberg connected e.V. (bwcon), a leading

business initiative for the promotion of the high-tech sectors. In addition, OND worked closely together with the Bavarian state, Bavarian Office for the Protection of the Constitution and the police for the sixth Workshop for Innovation to work out the topic “Innovation Security in Photonics” related to the recent and ongoing hacker attacks on the European and especial German Photonics Industry.

The organization of the **European Photonics Start-up Challenge** did benefit from the co-operation with LUX Photonics Consortium as a sponsor, promoter and exploiter. Several universities, research institutes and founder and innovation centers throughout Germany promoted the event in co-operation with OND.

3.4 Italy

In the week 23-31 of October 2015, at MuSe, Museo delle Scienze in Trento, the “Photonics Week” was held in order to disseminate photonics. All the research/science actors present on the Trentino territory such as CNR, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, University of Trento, and Muse, collaborated for the organization of the event. The Institute of Photonics and Nanotechnology IFN CNR Trento, in the framework on the Photonics4All project, was actively involved in organizing some laboratory experiences for students also using the kit Photonics Explorer. A similar event was “Shine a Light” (8/11/2015 at MuSe, Trento).

The Photonics Explorer kit was also used during the European Researchers Night (MeetMeTonight, Milano 30 September 2016).

Other events were organized for teachers and students: "Officina Scuola" (Monselice, 9 September 2016), “Photonic Day” (Liceo “G. Galilei”, Trento, 21 October 2016) demonstrations (Liceo Scientifico Statale "Edoardo Amaldi", Alzano Lombardo (BG), March 2015 and March 2016).

3.5 Slovakia

Since 2015 ILC cooperated closely with the city of Bratislava. In 2015 the “Nuit Blanche” art festival moved for the first time to capital Bratislava. During this event 50 art projects illuminated Bratislava and were admired by more than 100,000 visitors. The team from ILC presented several installations, and developed the format of Festival of Light which was held in parallel to Nuit Blanche. It gained such a success that the city of Bratislava invited ILC and SEA agency (www.avv.sk) to develop the Festival of Light in Bratislava as completely independent event, which was delivered and attracted more than 50.000 visitors in three days of September 2016. In particular, the vice-mayor of the City of Bratislava, Dr. Iveta Plšeková, and the mayor of the Old Town Mgr. Radoslav Števíčik actively promoted this event at press-conference as well as during the Night of Researchers, and are supporting the further development of the Festival of light in 2017 and beyond. In this regard it is

noteworthy to say that the concept of this festival is based on collaboration of photonics-related companies, town representatives (including conservation, history and archeological institutes) and young artists in the public space, sharing the common vision of Light and Photonics as technology for better living in the town of the future.

Another large-scale event that has been actively supported by Photonics4all was Night of Researchers in Slovakia - a national festival promoting research to the general public and students, organized by SOVVA (Slovak Organization for Research and Development Activities, www.sovva.eu). In 2016 the ILC became official partner of this event with the dedicated facility (Orange FabLab) opened for dissemination of OmniLight laboratory technologies and Photonics in general during the Night of Researchers 2016.

Figure 6: Cooperation with authorities in Slovakia

*Vice-mayor of the City of Bratislava, Dr. I. Pišková, M. Atanasová (SEA agency)
and D. Chorvát (ILC) at the Night of Researchers promoting the Festival of Light in Bratislava.*

Further important collaboration was established with the National Centre for Popularization of science and technology in Society in Bratislava, part of the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information (SCSTI). The SCSTI is a subsidiary

organization (public body) of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic, established in 1938 as the Slovak technical library and now is the national information centre for science, technology, innovation and education and specialized scientific library of the Slovak Republic. It coordinates activities and ensures the operation of interdisciplinary R&D centers and national infrastructures for research, development, innovation and education. It is the host institution of the National Contact Points for HORIZON 2020 and ensures operation of the Slovak Liaison Office for R&D in Brussels. ILC collaborated with SCSTI in organization of Photonics Workshop for teachers in 2015 and also during the Week of science of Technology in November 2015 which was dedicated to Light and light-based technologies. Since 2016 we are in close collaboration within the project of the Science Centre Aurelium, which host many exhibits dedicated to light, photonics, information technology, physics and related fields developed by, or under the guidance of ILC experts. Use of the OmniLight laboratory (OLL) prototype in this Science centre for public lectures and shows is one of the marketing strategies that we decided for the sustainable OLL development after the Photonics4all project.

3.6 Sweden

EaPS cooperated with the Museum Gustavianum in Uppsala at the Lightday (Ljusdagen – 28th of November 2015). PhotonicSweden moderated the talks at the workshops and talks held during the day.

EaPS cooperated with the municipality of Alingsås for the Photonics4All campaign. Alingsås is open to experiment with different lighting designs for public buildings and entered into agreements with the Professional Lighting Designers' Association - PLDA, who have brought the international world of lighting design to Alingsås every October since then. The result is an educational and fun lighting event which has grown annually. It all starts with a practical workshop one week before the event opens for the public where also EaPS held a one day seminar on Photonics. This is when experienced lighting designers from all over the world gathers in Alingsås along with 60 international students of lighting design and architecture. Together, they create well lit outdoor environments in just six days. Throughout the years, the workshop teams have illuminated everything from parks to ponds, churches and cemeteries, houses and backyards; a wide variety of typical urban spaces.

EaPS cooperated with the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), NCC, Open Lab, IVL Svenska Miljöinstitutet, Stockholms stad and Uniarts to put life into the Dome of Visions by organizing the Light festival in the DOME OF VISIONS (23rd - 28th of November 2015) and the Lighting visions: light, space and nature on the 9th of December 2015 with workshops and presentations.

Figure 7: Light festival in the DOME OF VISIONS in 2015

3.7 The Netherlands

TUD has brought the Project in Light with the “Light Room” at the Science Center in Delft. We have made several experiments with their explanation to help kids and grow-up to discover the wonder of Light. The *Photonics4all* project is also presented as well as the PhotonicsApp and the bookmarks. The video is shown on a screen in the room.

Figure 1: Hand-on experiments in the Science Center of the Delft University of Technology

TUD is also in cooperation with PhotonicsNL, the Dutch portal for optics and photonics professionals. We have been invited to participate to the Photonics Events the last two years to give presentation about the project and be presents are our both to deliver information and brochures.

TUD has been a partner in the event of Lichtsavond in the city of Delft (2015 and 2016) with experiments and demonstration on a booth location in the city center of Delft.

3.8 United Kingdom

The Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council Centre for Manufacturing in Photonics (CIMP) purchased 10 Photonics explorer kits for the UoS and the National Future Photonics Manufacturing Hub purchased the remainder. The Hub has agreed to fund a further 20 kits and workshops in the year 2017-2018 and will fund Photonics Outreach activities until 2020. A close partnership was formed with the Institute of Physics and the South of England's Regional Mathematics and Science Learning Centre (teacher training centre) in order to train teachers to use the kits. This will be an on-going partnership to deliver more teacher training sessions with both organisations.

The Children's University at the UoS was delivered with the support of the OSA/SPIE Student Chapter.

The UoS worked closely with the Royal Horticultural Society to deliver their Tatton Park Garden Show Reflecting Photonics Outreach Campaign 21-24.07.2015 which was mentioned at the UK IYL2015 Closing Ceremony at the Royal Society by the IOP. Moreover, UoS give two Photonics Lectures and promoted Photonics4All at the London Science Museum 'Lates' to an audience of 240 adults on 27.05.15 and featured at the OCR School Exam Board's teacher's conference at the Royal Institution, London on 16.06.2016 where they had a booth. Last but not least, UoS had the opportunity to distribute bookmarks to Prof Sir Bill Wakeham who is UK Chair

of the British-Italian Partnership Programme and Vice-President of the Royal Academy of Engineering.

3.9 Multilateral cooperation

Besides, the consortium cooperated with the UN/UNESCO for the International Year of Light (IYL). For instance, the Photonics4All video was shown at the closing ceremony in Mexico and the IYL ambassador of the UN, John Dudley.

European Centres for Outreach in Photonics (ECOP) also included Photonics4All in its “Resources” section on its website and collaborated with Photonics4all in organization of many joined events in Slovakia during the IYL 2015..

Scientix, the community for Science and Education has included information on Photonics4All tools for teachers and young people in its project list. The information on the project is available in English, German, Spanish, French, Dutch, Italian, Polish and Rumanian. Scientix promotes and supports a Europe-wide collaboration among STEM (science, technology, engineering and maths) teachers, education researchers, policymakers and other STEM education professionals.

The international society for optical engineering SPIE disseminates Photonics4All tools & activities in its “Educational Outreach Resources” section.

The Optical Society (OSA) has included Photonics4All in its “Youth Education Resources” section.

The European Physical Society (EPS) has included Photonics4All in its educational resources section.

The European Technology Platform Photonics21 has included a whole page on Photonics4All in its “Training & Education” section as well.

In addition, the Photonics4All project is continuously networking with its fellow Photonics PPP CSA projects, widely communicating about the projects’ tools and activities in the photonics community in a sustainable way all the more are the project partners are all involved in other photonics projects and will continue to promote the results beyond the project lifetime.

4 Cooperation with photonics enterprises/industry

Close cooperation with the photonics industry was obtained by the consortium as most of the partners are clusters or technology transfer organisations and do have a big network of industrial members (e.g. OptecNet Deutschland).

4.1 Germany

For the Photonics4All **start-up challenge**, Photonics4All managed to get the company [nanoscribe](#), [LUX Photonics Consortium](#) and "[Berlin Adlershof](#)" as main sponsors. Besides, OND convinced the "[Messe Berlin GmbH](#)" to support the start-up challenge at their premises (stage in third hall) and "[Berlin Partner](#)" with catering as well as "[WISTA Management GmbH](#)" to offer a Tour in the Business- and Technology Center Berlin Adlershof and "[EPIC](#)" to promote the challenge and report about the winner in their network. The journal "[Photonik](#)" with a number of copies of approx. 17,000 will report about the winner and its innovative technology. In addition, the regional photonics network of the respective partners agreed to promise a free one-year membership (a regional network of OptecNet Germany, Opticsvalley in France, PhotonicSweden, Future Manufacturing Photonics Hub, Slovak Photonics Cluster or Photonics Austria). For further information on the European Photonics Start-up challenge, please refer to D2.8.

Figure 8: Logos of partners and sponsors of the European Start-up challenge

Figure 9: The winner of the European Photonics Start-up Challenge Sicoya GmbH

For the **Innovation Workshops** with round 500 attendees and especially more than 150 from SMEs, OND worked closely together with representatives of the attending companies to adjust the workshops content and the development of the “Guide – Open Innovation in Photonics”. Five of the six Innovation Workshops took place at companies (Automotive Lighting Reutlingen GmbH, Dioptic GmbH and kdg OPTICOMP (Austria)) and research organization branches of members of OND. The hosts organized company tours as well as the presentation of best practice regarding innovation in photonics.

Figure 10: Impressions from the 3rd innovation workshop – “Precision mounting of photonic micro systems”

A lot of attendees mentioned, that they could establish personal contacts from these Workshops for further potential co-operations. At the end of the Workshops, ten of them agreed in **five partnership agreements** to further evaluate interests regarding e.g. manufacturing, technical co-operation or research co-operation agreements.

Some examples for co-operation with photonics enterprises/industry in the Workshops:

Abacus Laser
AEMtec GmbH
Albis Plastic GmbH
Automotive Lighting Reutlingen GmbH
Berliner Glas KGaA
camline
Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH
CAS Software GmbH
Coherent Laser Systems GmbH & Co.KG
Comsol Multiphysics GmbH
Deininger Laser
Dioptic GmbH
Dr. Haupt Optikentwicklung

iris GmbH
IST METZ GmbH
Jenoptik Polymer Systems GmbH
Jos. Schneider Optische Werke GmbH
Laser Optik GmbH
Medical Mountains AG
Pilz GmbH
Quioptiq Photonics GmbH & Co. KG
Richard Wolf GmbH
Roche Diagnostics GmbH
Siemens AG
Tektronix GmbH
Testo AG

FARO Europe GmbH & Co. KG
FCI GmbH
Feinoptik Drammetal GmbH
Innovavent GmbH

Throl Optics GmbH
Viaoptic GmbH
Visteon Electronics Germany GmbH
Z-Laser Optoelektronik GmbH

OptecNet Deutschland received such a good feedback, that further workshops will be organized after the project Photonics4All. The PDF version of the 'Guide – Open Innovation in Photonics' will be updated based on lessons learned during the workshops and uploaded on the websites of both Photonics4All and OptecNet Deutschland.¹ by the end of 2016. The gained experiences and the guidelines will also be promoted and transferred in other workshops and working groups.

Some regional photonics clusters will frequently organized working group meeting with mainly innovation, not technical content as planned in Baden-Württemberg and Berlin/Brandenburg and Lower-Saxony, if there will be enough attendees in the new conceptualized working groups with the main focus on innovation methods and processes. Other national, regional or sectorial networks are welcome to co-operate in cross-cluster activities and share the experiences to increase the impact.

4.2 France

In the framework of its activity regarding Photonics for Investment, Optisvalley has cooperated and will continue cooperating with SMEs, and in particular start-ups.

We organized or were partner to 2 major events on Photonics funding. The detailed description of these events (presentation, methodology, impact measurement & follow-up) is available in the Deliverable D2.9 "Conduct photonics for investment in France and Slovakia".

The first venture summit event took place on 13 June 2016. Opticsvalley organized the "Creative Business Cup" challenge for France in Paris on 13 June 2016. This Venture Summit was organized for Photonics start-ups. Opportunity has been given to the **13 start-ups** participating to identify financing opportunities, to pitch in front of 29 investors and to network and exhibit their products.

Company	Contact partner	Email
DAMAE Medical	Anais BARUT	anais.barut@gmail.com
MIRSENSE	Mathieu CARRAS	mathieu.carras@mirsense.com
NAPA TECHNOLOGIE S	Daniel TUROVER	daniel.turover@silsef.com
KEEN EYE	Sylvain BERLEMONT	sylvain.berlemont@keeneyetechnologies.c

¹ <http://optecnet.de/>

Company	Contact partner	Email
TECHNOLOGIE S		om
CHECKUP SOLAR	Luc MEHRET	luc.merhet@checkupsolar.com
LIGHTON	Laurent DAUDET	laurent.daudet@espci.fr
CASCADE LIGHT TECHNOLOGIE S	Frédéric PEILLERON	frederic.peilleron@lightcascade.fr
GREENTROPISM	Anthony BOULANGER	anthony.boulanger@greentropism.com
KUANTOM	Simon FALK	sfalk@cocktailsquare.com
ENOVAP	SCHECK Alexandre	a.scheck@enovap.com
AQUATIX	Alain DINIS	adinis@virtualdive.com
CYCLOPUS	Jérémie ABOU	jeremie.abou@cyclopus.net
DREAMUP VISION	Ekaterina BESSE	ekaterina.besse@dreamupvision.com

Table 2: List of participants to Opticsvalley's Photonics Venture Summit – pitching start-ups

Opticsvalley was also partner in the organization of the INPHO Venture Summit, the event for executives active in smart technologies including photonics and smart businesses in Bordeaux (6 & 7 October 2016).

This event gathers every 2 years large companies, venture capitalists and start-ups to meet to develop collaborations while exchanging on key bankable challenges to invest in.

In this year's edition, **31 SMEs** attended, and **29 start-ups**. These photonics companies were given the opportunity to pitch in front of investors, and to meet the investors during One to One meeting set-up for them in an open innovation framework.

Name of company	Country
BSQ Solar	Spain
XTPL	Poland
Cascade	France
BluemintLabs	France
ARYBALLE TECHNOLOGIES	France
Primo1D	France
Insightness	Switzerland
Drayson Technologies	UK
D-EYE	Italy
Argolight	France
DAMAE MEDICAL	France
VivoSensMedical	Germany
MedLumics	Spain

LunaLEC	Sweden
BeSpoon	France
itk	France
Chronocam	France
AEPONYX	Canada
EFFECT Photonics	Netherlands

Table 3: List of Start-ups pitching at INPHO Venture Summit in Bordeaux

Figure 11: The pitch award winner of INPHO 2016 is Chronocam

These 2 events are related here as they were important in terms of size, but a lot of other events dedicated to SMEs were organised during the project, where Photonics4All and its tools were presented: workshops, Welcome sessions, seminars etc. All the information can be found in the D4.7 “Matrix Events Tools”.

In total, more than 530 SMEs participated in the events where Opticsvalley represented Photonics and the project.

4.3 Slovakia

[KVANT](#), a private company developing and renting laser displays and scientific and educational tools for more than 20 years (<https://www.kvant.sk/lasers/about-us>) is the main industrial partner of ILC in developing the OmniLight laboratory. In fact, the project of OLL itself was based on the successful collaboration of ILC experts and Kvant during previous years, leading e.g. to fully interactive real-time laser show delivered now worldwide on commercial basis. Moreover, in 2015 Kvant became a general industrial partner of the Slovak Centre of

Scientific and Technical Information responsible for creation of the Science centre Aurelium (the first national science centre in Slovakia), where many exhibits developed in collaboration with ILC were dedicated for Photonics outreach and dissemination Several components are from KVANT (see picture).

Figure 12: Light show at the main hall of Science centre Aurelium

For technical development of OmniLight laboratory, as well as the Aurelium science centre, we ILC collaborated also closely with SiProgs software development studio.

Since several years ILC organized the Day of Photonics, held annually on October 21st which is an event developed and promoted by EPIC association (European Photonics Industry Consortium). In Slovakia support of this event from GoPhoton! and Photonics4all projects meant sustainable development of industrial-academy platform in the form of emerging Slovak Photonics Cluster initiated and maintained by ILC. In 2015, as the national highlight of the International year of light and light based technologies, the Day of photonics was organized under the auspices of the Minister of education, science, research, and sport of the Slovak Republic. In 2015 and 2016 following companies actively contributed to the event as well as to the activities of the cluster (at the moment still informal network of companies and academic institutions):

- Sylex s.r.o.
- Avantek s.r.o.
- Prva Zvaracska a.s.
- Kvant s.r.o.

- MicroStep s.r.o.
- Photoneo s.r.o.
- Carl Zeis Slovakia s.r.o.
- PowerTec s.r.o.
- LEDeco solution s.r.o.
- NMS s.r.o.
- Oncological Institute of St Elisabeth

Figure 13: Presentation of Photoneo s.r.o. during the Day of Photonics 2016

4.4 Great Britain

Tatton Park show: The conceptual garden, was sponsored by the Optoelectronics Research Centre at University of Southampton (ORC), CED Ltd, SureSet UK Ltd, Dural Ltd, Barcham Trees plc and Grange Fencing Ltd, reflected the world-leading research into light-transmitting optical fiber by the University of Southampton. The UoS worked closely with the designer Elks-Smith Landscaping. The Outreach event which included researchers promoting their research in the garden was partially funded by the EPSRC Centre for Innovative Manufacturing in Photonics. Photonics4All newsletters and tools were distributed via the South East Photonics Network to 400 local Photonics Companies and the Photonics4All Start-Up Competition promoted at the UoS Photonics Industry Day.

Figure 14 Elks-Smith Landscaping Designers visit the ORC, and Booth at RHS Tatton Park Garden Show

Figure 15 Media Coverage of the Reflecting Photonics Garden at Tatton Park

4.5 Sweden

PhotonicSweden (EaPS) cooperated extensively with the industry/SMEs as a lot of members come out of this category. Our members contributed to the events we carried out either by sponsoring equipment or by exhibiting and showing hands-on exhibits for the General Public. For the children's universities they provided equipment and sponsored the food.

4.6 The Netherlands

TUD is the initiator of the dutch initiative DOC (Dutch Optics Center) which brings companies related to Optics together to solve problems for the future. The project photonics4all has been presented to the opening ceremony (19 October 2016) and has attracted a lot of attention to the companies present and the officials (Ministry of Economic Affairs).

4.7 Multilateral cooperation

Photonics4All participated with a booth at the Annual Meeting of Photonics21, the European Public Private Partnership in Optics & Photonics, in Brussels on 2-3 March 2016. Fabio Chiarello from CNR gave a special presentation in Working Group 7 of the PPP to present the outstanding results of the game competition. A vivid discussion on IPR and dissemination possibilities followed. Besides, Photonics21 dedicated a special section on its website to our project and regularly publishes news about Photonics4All.

In addition, Photonics4All has collaborated with several other EU projects, one of them specifically targeting SMEs: RespiceSME. This project aims at reinforcing the innovative capacity of Europe's photonics Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), clusters and national platforms by stimulating targeted collaborations in and beyond

photonics. Photonics4All and RespiceSMEs have been collaborating in open innovation support using the tools (Innovation offer, Innovation request and partnership agreement templates) developed in Photonics4All.

Photonics4All is also collaborating with further Photonics PPP CSA projects targeted (among other) at SMEs, such as EuroPHo21, Laser-Go, PICs4All (already running projects) and EPRISE (starting in January 2017).

5 Summary

Collaboration with EYESTvzw

In summary:

- More than 290 Photonics Explorer kits were sold and distributed, representing about 10% of the total number of kits distributed by EYEST so far
- 1 partner (PhAu) was already and 3 partners (CNR, TUD, UoS) became “local associated partners” of EYEST, in charge of teachers’ trainings and of the distribution of kits in their country/region.
- EYEST agreed to promote the Photonics4All App with a flyer in its kit.

Cooperation with public authorities and policy makers

As for the cooperation with authorities, this took place through the organization of a wide range of events such as:

- Teacher trainings and the cooperation with teacher training organisations (and the related ministries) (Austria)
- National events such as the EU Researcher Night (in Austria, Italy, Slovakia) or the French science festival “Fête de la science”
- Direct contacts with local universities and technical universities (e.g. in Austria, France, Germany) as well as with regional research foundations (Germany)
- Cooperation with art museums (Italy, Sweden, UK) and science centers (The Netherlands, Slovakia, UK)
- Cooperation with local authorities (municipality representatives) for the organisation of big photonics outreach public events (e.g. in Slovakia, Sweden)
- Direct contact with cooperation with science outreach authorities (UK, Slovakia)
- The contact with international big players such as Photonics21, ECOP, SPIE, OSA, Scientix.

Cooperation with photonics enterprises/industry

In total, more than thousand SMEs were reached in events organized and/or attended by Photonics4all partners, about 350 of them being actively involved in open innovation events (innovation workshops) and fund raising activities (the European Photonic start-up challenge and investment events). One special case shall be highlighted here with the cooperation with the private company Kvant for the development of a Photonics4All product, the OmniLight laboratory, in Slovakia.